

PORTRAYAL OF TRADITION AND MODERNITY OF WOMEN IN BHARATHY MUKHERJEE'S THE TIGER'S DAUGHTER

¹ Mrs. Mercy Nava Jothi, ² Ms. G. Shanmugapriya, M.A., M.Phil

¹ M.Phil Research Scholar, ² Assistant Professor,

^{1,2} Department of English

^{1,2} Ponnaiyah Ramajayam Institute of Science and Technology,

^{1,2} PRIST Deemed to be University,

¹ mercynavajothi24@gmail.com, ² priyadharshni325@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Indian English writing was valued in the hands of women writers only after a great deal of battle, thanks to the bias that they wrote about what they had experienced. They largely dealt with female subjectivity, domestic space, and personal sorrow, among other things. In recent years, these female writers have made fruitful attempts to experiment with a variety of genres, helping them to establish themselves as strong and distinct voices in the literary world. There was a vast range of issues covered in their works, giving readers a sense of variety and individuality. In order to bring literature to its current status, some noteworthy individuals laboured persistently over a long period of time. Women's writing is increasingly recognised as a prominent and influential modernist media, particularly in the United States. The incredible accomplishment of these writers in carving out a place for themselves has altered the way women's literature is seen today. In their writings, these authors address the most pressing issues and sensitive areas of life, such as the search for one's own identity and feminine sensibility, bridging the gap between tradition and modernity, and so forth.

Keywords : *portrayal , tradition , modernity ,women , bharathy mukherjee's.*

INTRODUCTION

Contemporary women writers recognise the importance of responding to the requirements of their day

by making successful attempts to win over the public through their writings, and they have spoken out about it publicly. Today's women are no longer confined to the confines of the home, but have emerged as active participants in society's various realms, including politics, business, and academia. Women's sorrows and traumas have been written about extensively, as have the complexities of men-woman relationships, social and personal obstacles, and other subjects relating to male-dominated civilizations.

A Bengali by birth, she completed her undergraduate studies at the University of Calcutta in 1958 and postgraduate studies at the University of Baroda in 1961 before relocating to the United States of America, where she studied for her MFA and Ph.D. degrees and remained for more than three decades as a member of the American contingent at the University of Iowa. Despite her lengthy stay, familial ties strongly bond her to her place of origin, forcing her to emphasise her status as an American writer in order to maintain her independence.

Despite the fact that she was born and nurtured in Calcutta, she said, "the city will stay a habit with me," adding, "but as a writer, I have evolved completely in the United States." Mukherjee began her writing career in 1971 and has been published in numerous publications. She has six works of fiction to her credit, which are as follows: The Tiger's Child is a fictional character created by the author of the novel The Tiger's Child. Two

women: 1) Wife, and 2) Nightmare 4) "The Middleman," as well as other stories Jasmine, 5) The Holder of the World, and 6) The Middlemen and Other Stories, the latter of which earned her the National Book Critics Circle Award for The Middlemen and Other Stories in 1980. Without a doubt, his works such as Tiger's Daughter, Wife, and Darkness deal sensitively with the issue of immigration in the United States of America.

THE TIGER'S DAUGHTER

He also represents the delicate collision of two worlds (the East and the West), which are attempting to grasp one another through his works. A Brahmin girl educated at Vassar College (in the United States of America) and married to an American, Tara returns to Calcutta and rediscovers the culture of her people in The Tiger's Daughter. "Wife" is a narrative of Dimple and her husband, Amit Basu, who moved to New York from their native India in order to live in an ethnically appropriate slum.

In her latest work, Jasmine, the novelist is not restricted to either India or the United States of America, but she does so in a broad stroke of imagination. Ayesha Kegal contributes the following: Wife and Darkness, a collection of short stories, is a collection of short stories that achieve electrifying speed in Middleman, **"she is a writer of exquisite talent, and the 'urgency,' and 'energy,' of which she speaks, is evident in her most recent work" (p.298).** Her prior novels, The Tiger's Daughter and Wife, are set in India and deal with the experiences of being an Indian expatriate and an American immigrant, respectively, in those countries.

She has made the journey from being an expatriate to becoming an American immigrant through the role of Tara in The Tiger's Daughter, and through the portrayal of Dimple in Wife, she has made the journey from being an expatriate to being an American immigrant. In Darkness, she identifies as a full-fledged immigrant. Bharati Mukherjee's work is primarily about

Indian women who, via their writing, explore the meaning of life in a way that Indian women writers have done for centuries, whether in English or in her native language. Displacement and place are two of the most prominent themes in postcolonial literature.

The inability to forge a connection between oneself and one's environment results in an identity crisis. Ethnic women in the United States are clearly marginalised on two fronts: the basis of their ethnicity and their gender. Mukherjee's central characters, Tara, Dimple, and Jasmine, fight two parallel battles against marginalisation during their early expatriate experiences in America; coming from (an)other world, their very identities are called into question in America, begging to be revised and re-defined from the outset.

In the exercise's main stream movement, the times of transition, metamorphosis, and reincarnation are significant because the exercise is aggressive and powerful, and its echos on the fringes help to legitimise expatriation fears. When Mukherjee's ladies finally emerge, the characteristics that distinguish them represent the emergence of a whole new species in modern society: the "ethnic" who is also "American." Making sense of their identities must be a struggle: a struggle with the self, a struggle with tradition, a struggle with the beauty and tragedy that come with living in a new society, a struggle with emerging aspirations, hopes, and desires.

It is only after a long struggle that Bharati Mukherjee's ladies find their own voices, but not before they have struggled against perceptions of themselves as "otherness" - exotic yet mute, capable yet restrained. Certainly, as Mukherjee's ladies advance from the lonely Tara, who returns home to find herself strangely isolated, to the free Jyoti – Jasmine – Jase – Jane, who makes a lifetime – for – everyone seem like a possibility for any cheerful immigrant, more and more is left out.

The cultural confrontation between the East and the West is shown in Mukherjee's debut novel, The

Tiger's Daughter, which is her first novel. The protagonist of the novel is an Indian woman who, after relocating to the United States of America, endures cultural shock. For the most part, the novel is a creative reflection of Bharati Mukherjee's actual experience of travelling to the West and the aftereffects of the culture shock she suffered throughout her travels. It is an autobiographical representation of the author herself as Tara Banarjee Cartwright, who is married to an American and lives in New York City with her husband.

After reading *The Tiger's Daughter*, Mukherjee may notice that she has more than an Indian pulse pulsating in her, despite the fact that she styles herself as an American author. It appears that her Indian heritage has been strongly instilled in her. We can observe the typical Bengali spirit throughout the novel, which can be noticed in her use of traditional Indian expressions, in a number of different situations throughout the story. In the novel, the protagonist's practise of preserving her maiden surname after marriage symbolically depicts her subconscious mentality, which is still strongly rooted in her native country and has not been able to forget it despite her adoption of a European national identity. Tara's mentality is a wonderful amalgamation of Americanness and Indianness, and she is a fascinating character.

Tara is the *Tiger's Daughter*, and she is a student at Poughkeepsie High School in New York. While at Poughkeepsie, Tara, who was missing her family, believed she was being discriminated against if her roommate did not share her mango chutney. She was very protective of her family and her country. The American's New York was incredible and drove her to despair: "on days when she feared she couldn't possibly survive, she had shaken out all her silk scarves, ironed them, and hung them to make the flat look more Indian." **She prayed to Kali for strength so that she wouldn't collapse. (p.34)** Tara met and fell in love with an American named David Cartwright, and the two eventually married. As a result

of her marriage to David, who was a tremendously western man, Tara was unable to convey the finer nuances of her family's heritage and existence in Calcutta to David. Her husband questioned about Indian customs and traditions in an inane manner. She was completely uneasy in a strange place, and she felt completely vulnerable. **"Madison Square was a nightmare, and her husband was a foreigner after all," says the author (p.38).** Tara returns to India after a seven-year stay in the subcontinent. A foreign western culture that has practically taken on the role of a second personality in Tara's life comes into conflict with the culture of her home country when she travels to India at the age of twenty-two. Tara's mental state is significantly altered as a result of the crash, as she tries to adjust to her Indian friends and relatives, as well as to the traditions of her own family.

It is the fact that she is alone in her own nation that is the most ironic aspect of her return. Certainly, her new ego is to blame for the disruption in her enjoyment, but the deteriorating societal changes as well as her new perspective on India's poverty and filth only serve to increase her discomfort, annoyance, and disgust even further. Tara had hoped that her return to India would soothe her displeasure with her time spent in the United Kingdom. Her first step onto the Indian subcontinent, in the city of Bombay, left her feeling underwhelmed. Bombay is the same as before, but her point of view has evolved. The Bombay railway station, according to her, **"looked more like a hospital, with so many sick and misshapen individuals sitting listlessly on bundles and turnks" (p.14)** Her current sickness drives her to reminisce about her late husband and father, David.

A reference to the formation of her second personality is made in the concept of her marriage. It looks that she has become more at ease with the unusual planet she has discovered. When Tara travels by train from Bombay to Calcutta, she is subjected to an equally awful experience. Everything has changed and

deteriorated in Calcutta, as well as the rest of India. As a result of riots triggered by a collision between different socioeconomic strata, Calcutta, where she has now found herself, is embroiled in carnage as a result of her arrival.

That dashes her Calcutta dreams and causes her to react negatively as a result of it. With time, her changing personality causes her to become an outcast in the company of her friends and relatives, and she is unable to participate in the ritual functions of the home as well. Tara is shown as an Indian-American, and because she sees India through the eyes of an American, she is socially and psychologically isolated from the rest of the world. Tara's marriage is the most major source of her unhappiness, as it hangs as a burden on her heart: Tara's intellect is constantly at conflict with the two personas she carries, one Indian and the other American. She also feels herself to be an outcast in whatever situation she finds herself in.

She tries her hardest to be Indian and fit in with her friends, but there is an unseen barrier between them, and she senses a breakdown coming upon her. She is obliged to investigate her inner world, which is comprised of two cultures and two diametrically opposed beliefs that are as diametrically opposed as two words can be separated. After realising that a reconciliation with David is unattainable, Tara longs to be reunited with him. The summer she spends in Darjeeling with her father, Begal Tiger, is meant to be entertaining for her, but Tara finds neither solace or peace in the mountainous region. Consequently, Tara's journey to India, her ancestral home, proves difficult and ultimately results in her delusion, estrangement, sorrow, and tragic conclusion.

Her longing to return to New York and find a place to call home where she might find love and security ends in ironic disappointment. Tara, in her own way, embodies not just the Indian expatriate, but also the modernity crisis: **"Tara is a typical figure not only of the Indian expatriate, but also of the modernity crisis:**

When modernity heralds the end of a more ancient process of filiation rooted in culture and heredity, the goal for her is to find some form of affiliation and thus develop ties that, while not as long-lasting and enduring, allow for greater freedom and flexibility".
(Says number 61)

CONCLUSION

As the narrative comes to a close, she remains true to her feelings for David and to the decision she has made to live her life in the manner in which she does: **"The paradox persists, but no one is torn asunder."** Clark (p235) defines formalised formalised Due to Bharati Mukherjee's unique weaving together of the narrative line with diverse perspectives – Indian, feminine, and immigrant – the traditional thematic core of expatriate writing, the conflict between the native and the alien, "self" and "the other," appears to have gained new richness and complexity in her novelistic vision.

REFERENCES

- [1]. "Introduction" to Bharati Mukherjee's Fiction, edited by R.K. Dhawan (Routledge). In 1991, Prestige Books published Indian Women Novelists, Volume I, Series I. Prestige Books was founded in New Delhi in 1991.
- [2]. The Text, the World, and the Critic by Edward Said was published by Routledge and Kegan Paul in New York in 1986.
- [3]. 3. Bharati Mukherjee: Critical Perspectives, edited by Spivak and published by Garland Publishing in New Delhi in 1993.
- [4]. The Journal of Indian Scholar published Padma, T.'s article, "Diaspora, Multiple Identities, and Metamorphosis: A Critique of Bharati Mukherjee's Novels," in Volume 15, Number 2, July 1993.